

Effect of Thickness, Doping Concentration and Temperature on Output Electric Properties of Thin Film Silicon Solar Cell

Raed M. Humaidan ✉

General Directorate of Education Salahaddin, Salahaddin, Iraq

Falah Mohammed Abed

Al-Dour Technical Institute, Northern Technical University, Iraq

Naziha N. Aneizan

General Directorate of Education Salahaddin, Salahaddin, Iraq

Article History:

Received: 15.03.2026 Revised: 27.03.2026 Accepted: 30.03.2026 Published: 02.04.2026

ABSTRACT:

Recently, international companies are competing to improve solar cells efficiency and support research that contributes to the development of solar cell techniques. The main objective of this work is to design a model of a silicon solar cell consisting of two layers, n- type emitter layer and p- type base layer, by pc1d simulation program. Solar cell performance can be evaluated by doing deep analysis on many effective parameters, such as thickness, doping concentration level, temperature etc. for each layer. Where the thickness and doping level of emitter layer were changed from (0-0.1) μm , (10^{14} - 10^{20}) cm^{-3} , respectively. Also, the effect of thickness and doping level for the base layer from (0-5) μm , (10^{15} - 10^{19}) cm^{-3} , respectively. It investigates the effect of temperature within the range (25- 60) $^{\circ}\text{C}$ on solar cell performance, containing short circuit current, open circuit voltage and conversion efficiency. As the ideal electrical characteristic of the solar cell obtained are, $I_{sc}=32.2$ mA, $V_{oc}=0.5415\text{V}$, $F.F=70.3\%$, $\eta=12.57\%$.

Keywords: solar cell, emitter layer, base layer, thin film.

Suggested Citation: R.M. Humaidan, F.M. Abed, N.N. Aneizan, "Effect of Thickness, Doping Concentration and Temperature on Output Electric Properties of Thin Film Silicon Solar Cell," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 4(2), pp. 229-237, Mar-Apr 2026. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2026.4(2).15

INTRODUCTION

Because of the serious worldwide environmental problem and the increasing energy consumption, photovoltaic generation attracts more and more attention, especially solar cells. Solar cells are manufactured from semiconductor materials; that is, materials that act as insulators at low temperatures, but as conductors when energy or heat is available. The most mature technology is silicon, so this is what most solar cells are. Silicon solar cells have been around and in use for decades. High cost and low conversion efficiency are two key barriers that would hinder the large-scale application of semiconductor solar cells. Given that the production cost and conversion efficiency are strongly related to the characteristics of silicon solar cells, optimizing their performance is critical [1]. Simulation of the electrical and optical properties of semiconductor devices recently arose as an indispensable auxiliary for optimization of existing devices and design of novel ones.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

The increasing number of numerical calculations made in order to properly understand the physical operating principles of solar cells. The process of physically testing silicon solar cells through simulation is expensive and time-consuming. These simulation programs have to follow the recent progress of experimental work, theoretical models, and available computing situations. PC1D has a 20 year history of development. PC1D v5 has received updates to increase accuracy and speed [2] and runs on 32-bit Windows computers. The program introduces new physical models, which broadens the applicability of simulation results; the run itself is significantly faster; and finally, the user interface has been upgraded, making running the program easier and decreasing occurrence of parameter input errors.

THEORIES

Solar or photovoltaic cell is a type of semiconductor devices that converts sunlight directly into electricity through the photovoltaic effect. So, the photovoltaic effect is a phenomenon that occurs when the energy of photons absorbed by the semiconductor material exceeds its band gap, creating electron-hole pairs that can be collected and converted into electricity. If the photon energy is equal to when higher than the band gap of the semiconductor material, it will output that amount of energy on absorption to photons incident at the semiconductor surface. Resulting in excitation of an electron from valence band into conduction band in generating excess charge carrier [3, 4].

The working principle behind solar cell operation is divided into three important parts. First is the absorption of light which results to generation of electron-hole pair which acts as the mobile charge carriers in the solar cell. Second is the transport mechanism which splits the mobile charge carriers called electrons and holes into the proper section of the solar cell in order to be collected. And the third is collection of electrons and holes which is done by the metal contacts that are situated on the front and back of solar cells and transfer the collected energy into the load. Understanding the fundamental principles of various phenomenon that occurs during these 3 processes and the factors that are affecting them will help us understand and design a more efficient solar cell [3, 5]. The basic working principle most solar cells are based on P-N junction. Intentionally adding impurities to a semiconductor can significantly alter its electrical properties. The process of intentionally adding impurities into an intrinsic (pure) semiconductor to alter its electrical property is called doping [5, 6]. The number of charge carriers are directly proportional to the level of doping in a semiconductor material. The majority charge carriers in N-type materials are negatively charged electrons while in P-type materials, the majority charge carriers are positively charged holes. When joined together, they create a PN junction which is the fundamental structure of modern crystalline silicon solar cells that are widely used globally [6].

Figure 1 shows the working principle behind PN junction solar cells.

Figure 1. Working Principle of PN Junction Solar Cells

Due to the difference of majority and minority charge carriers of P and N type silicon at the interface, a depletion region is formed due to the combination of electrons and holes which results to an induced electric field. This induced electric field can influence the movements of minority charge carriers in both region P and N region due to the drift transport mechanism. The minority charge carriers of N region (holes) are transported into the direction of the electric field (N to P) while the electrons in the P region are transported into the direction which is opposite of the electric field. This results to higher number of mobile charge carriers in both region which results to a higher probability of collection by the electrode or metal contact.

There are several parameters that measures the light to electricity conversion performance of a solar cell. The four most important measures of solar cell performance are the short circuit current (J_{sc}), open circuit voltage (V_{oc}), fill factor and efficiency. These factors can be determined by the isotropic curve (J-V) under the conditions illumination, as shown in Figure 2 [7, 8].

Figure 2. J-V Curve Characteristic of Solar Cell with and without Illumination
Source: [8]

Short circuit current (J_{sc}) is the maximum current that can be produced by the solar cell when there's no voltage (short circuited). It is the difference between the total current generated by photon and the current that is generated by the diode in the dark. The solar cell behaves like a diode when there's no illumination. Under illumination, the light source acts a current source due to its current generating capabilities. J_{sc} can be solved by using the following equations [3, 6].

$$I_{sc} = I_{ph} - I_o (e^{(qV/kT)} - 1) \quad (1)$$

$$J_{sc} = \frac{I_{sc}}{A} \quad (2)$$

The total current generated in a solar cell is directly proportional to the area of the solar cell, the larger the area, the higher amount of current will be generated. Another important factor in determining the value of the J_{sc} is the temperature T in kelvins. I_o is the reverse saturation current at temperature T , the value of I_o increases as the temperature rises. The constants V , q and k are voltage across the diode, the electric charge and Boltzmann's constant.

The open circuit voltage of a solar cell (V_{oc}) is the maximum voltage that can be obtained when the short-circuit current is zero [9].

$$V_{oc} = \frac{k_B T}{q} \ln \left(\frac{J_{ph}}{J_o} + 1 \right) \quad (3)$$

Fill factor (FF) is the ratio between the maximum theoretically obtainable power over the actual maximum obtainable power in a solar cell [10]. Equation (4) shows the equation in determining the fill factor of a solar cell.

$$FF = \frac{I_{mp} \times V_{mp}}{V_{oc} \times I_{sc}} \quad (4)$$

Efficiency is the most widely used measurement criteria in comparing the performance of different types of solar cells. Efficiency is the ratio of the actual power generated by the solar cell over the actual input energy (irradiance) from the sun (P_{in}). This performance metric is usually obtained using standard test conditions under A.M 1.5G global spectral irradiance. Equation (5) shows how to determine the efficiency of a solar cell.

$$\eta = \frac{V_{oc} \times I_{sc} \times FF}{P_{in}} \quad (5)$$

DESIGNED AND SIMULATION

PC1D (Personal Computer One Dimensional) is the computer program which simulates crystalline semiconductor devices. It prefers to be used for photovoltaic devices. PC1D is widely used for modelling crystalline solar cells. This software was developed by the University of New South Wales, Australia. The ideal parameter for a good solar cell using PC1D has been described in the literature [11]. The monolithic splitter is designed for the silicon solar cell which consists of two layers, the emitter layer and base layer, as shown in Figure 3. In order to obtain the optimal design of the solar cell, by studying the effect of the thickness, doping concentration and temperature of solar cell. The thickness of the emitter layer and background doping level were changed from (0-0.1) μm , ($10^{14} - 10^{20} \text{cm}^{-3}$), respectively by icon batch in pc1d software, and the base layer thickness and background doping level were changed from (0-300) μm , ($10^{15} - 10^{19} \text{cm}^{-3}$), respectively. The temperature of the solar cell varied from (25, 35, 40, 50 and 60) $^{\circ}\text{C}$. When simulating, we choose a typical model of silicon solar cell. Figure 3 shows the schematic of silicon solar cell model. It is a 1- cm^2 silicon solar cell which includes series resistance and shunt conductance, and has a shallow diffused emitter that has been pyramidally textured. The front reflectance is 10% across the solar spectrum. Table 1 shows several parameters of silicon solar cell model.

Figure 3. The Scheme of the Silicon Solar Cell Model

After simulation for n-Si/p-Si solar cell, by parameters as shown in table (1), using PC1D program, where to obtained on the optimizing of thickness, doping concentration level and temperature.

Table 1. Structure Parameters of Typical n-si/p-si Solar Cell

Parameters	Value
Device area	1cm ²
Front surface texture depth	3 μm
Rear surface texture depth	3 μm
Exterior front reflectance	10%
Emitter contact	1 × 10 ⁻⁶
Base contact	1 × 10 ⁻⁶
Thickness of emitter layer N- cSi	0.002μm
Thickness base layer P- cSi	300 μm
Back ground doping of emitter layer	1 × 10 ²⁰ cm ⁻³
Back ground doping of base	1 × 10 ¹⁶ cm ⁻³
Band gap of Si	1.12 eV
Dielectric constant	11.9
Intrinsic concentration at T=300K of Si	1 × 10 ¹⁰ cm ⁻³
Bulk recombination	$\tau_n = \tau_p = 7.208\mu s$
Front surface recombination	$S_n = S_p = 1 \times 10^6 \text{ cm/s}$
Rear surface recombination	$S_n = S_p = 1 \times 10^5 \text{ cm/s}$
Temperature of device	25 C ⁰
Primary light source	AM 1.5g spectrum
Excitation Mode	Transient
Base circuit	Sweep from -8 to 5 V

Results And Discussion

I-V Characteristic

After inserting the input parameters of the structure n-cSi/ p-cSi. The obtained results I-V curve is represented in Figure 4. The short circuit current (I_{SC}), open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}), and maximum power (Pmax) from the simulation can be used to calculate the fill factor and the efficiency of the solar cell. The result of the simulation of the PV cell at standard test conditions, temperature 25 C, irradiance 1,000 W/m², and AM1.5G, shown in Figure 4. With that condition, the current (I_{SC}) is 33.2mA, voltage (V_{OC}) is 0.5415 V, the power maximum is 0.01257W with the fill factor (FF) 70.3% and the efficiency 12.57%.

Figure 4. Current Voltage Curve of a Typical Solar Cell

Effect of Emitter Layer Thickness and Doping Concentration

The short circuit current density, open circuit voltage and the maximum efficiency and were calculated for the devices with varying emitter layer widths and doping concentration from (0-0.1)

μm , ($10^{14} - 10^{20} \text{cm}^{-3}$), respectively, with other parameters of the layer remaining constant. Figures 5 and 6 show the change of the short circuit current, open circuit voltage and the conversion efficiency of the silicon solar cell with the change in the thickness of the emitter layer. where we note that the highest value of the short circuit current is (33.17mA) and maximum of conversion efficiency was (12.57%) at the thickness (0.002) μm . As for open circuit voltage, its value was 541.38mV when the thickness was (0.002) μm and it started to increase slightly until it reached a value of 545.31mV with the increase in the thickness of the emitter layer. As we observed with increasing thickness of emitter layer, there was a gradual decrease in both the short circuit current and the conversion efficiency of the solar cell, this is due to the large decrease in the number of short wavelength photons available in the space charge region [12]. The n-Si emitter layer doping concentration level may affect the performance of the solar cell. Figures 7 and 8 show that as doping concentration level decreases below ($1 \times 10^{17} \text{cm}^{-3}$) the J_{SC} value sharply decreases, the conversion efficiency also decreases when decreasing doping concentration below ($1 \times 10^{17} \text{cm}^{-3}$). At lower doping concentrations, the electric field leads to accumulation of electron and hole carriers at the band offset of the valence and conduction band interface. Figures 7 and 8 show that with higher doping concentrations ($> 1 \times 10^{17} \text{cm}^{-3}$) in the emitter layer, both J_{SC} and conversion efficiency values increase. The depletion region builds up a higher barrier with higher electric field that facilitates minority carrier (electrons) diffusion from the absorber layer to emitter layer and to reach the front contact. Same thing occurs for the holes in the other side. This minority carrier diffusion results from the direction of electric field build-up caused by positive charges created in the n- Si and negative charges, Therefore, in a weak electric field, charge accumulation occurs leading to increased recombinations. In case of strong electric field, recombination rate is lowered as holes are driven away from the interface. Electrons, that reach the space charge region, are accelerated by this electric field towards the front contact [13]. Figures 7 and 8 show that at doping density $1 \times 10^{20} \text{cm}^{-3}$ or higher, in the n-Si emitter layer, the J_{SC} reaches higher than 33.17 mA/cm², conversion efficiency η reaches ~12.57%.

Figure 5. Effect of n- Si Emitter Layer Thickness on the Short Circuit Current

Figure 6. Effect of n- Si Emitter Layer Thickness on the Conversion Efficiency

Figure 7. Effect Doping Concentration Level of Emitter Layer on Short Circuit Current

Figure 8. Effect Doping Concentration Level of Emitter Layer on the Conversion Efficiency

Effect of Base Layer Thickness and Doping Concentration

The optimization of short circuit current J_{sc} and open circuit voltage V_{oc} have been investigated by varying the thickness of the base region from 0 μm to 300 μm (see Figure 9 and 10). As we notice that when the thickness of the base layer increases, both the short circuit current I_{sc} increased from 16.15 mA to 33.04 mA and the open circuit voltage increased slightly from 490.49mV to 543mV. The reason for this increase in the short circuit current and open circuit voltage is due to the increase in the thickness of the base layer, which leads to the absorption of the largest amount of photons falling on the cell, which contributes to the process of generating electron – hole pairs and thus increases the photocurrent [14]. The maximum I_{sc} and conversion efficiency is recorded 33mA and 12.57%, respectively at a 300 μm base thickness. Figure 11 shows the relationship between solar cell n-Si/p-Si Efficiency and thickness of the base layer. An increase in the thickness of the base layer from 0 to 300 μm is accompanied by an increase in the efficiency of the solar cell. The increase in the efficiency of solar cell is due to the increase in both the short circuit current and the open circuit voltage, according to equation (5) the conversion efficiency increases with increasing thickness [14]. The role of doping concentration in the conversion efficiency of the n-Si/p-Si solar cell is very important. Figure 12 shows the effect of doping concentration levels on efficiency. Doping levels range from $10^{15} - 10^{19} \text{cm}^{-3}$. Where we notice from the Figure 12 that the maximum efficiency of the solar cell was 12.57% with the doping concentration 10^{16}cm^{-3} and after this doping, the efficiency gradually decreases with increase in the doping concentration. The base layer with a higher doping density level possesses the high open circuit voltage and lowers the resistance, but it may also damage the lattice crystal [12]. Resulting in lower solar energy conversion efficiency cell with increase of doping concentration of the base region.

Figure 9. Short Circuit Current as a Function of Base Layer Thickness

Figure 10. Open Circuit Voltage as a Function of Base Layer Thickness

Figure 11. Conversion Efficiency as a Function of Base Layer Thickness

Figure 12. Conversion Efficiency as a Function of the Base Layer Doping Concentration

The Effect Temperature on the Out Put Electric Parameters of n- Si/p-Si Solar Cell

In this research we apply different temperature and the result of the I-V curve shown in Figure 13. The range of the temperature is 25 C° to 60 C°. It is shown that the temperature affects the current and the voltage of the solar cell. It means also the fill factor and efficiency affected. The most important parameter of silicon solar cell efficiency is open circuit voltage (Voc). It is function of temperature which is shown in equation (3). The Voc decreases as temperature increased as shown in Figure 14. The voltage is inversely proportional with the temperature. Since the temperature increases, the voltage will decrease. However, the current is directly proportional to the temperature as shown in Figure 15. The temperature increase will slightly increase the current of the solar cell. This is because of the more electron-hole pairs excited in the devices. The conversion efficiency of the solar cell gradually decreases with increases of temperature from 25 C° to 60 C°, due to increase of open circuit voltage according to the equation 5, as shown in Figure 16. Summarized the results of the PC1D simulation, it is clearer that temperature affects the performance of the solar cell. Since the temperature rises, the performance will decrease. It includes efficiency, the open-circuit voltage and short circuit current. The best performance gain at 25 C° where the efficiency is 12.57% with the open circuit voltage (0.5415 V) and short circuit current is 0.0332 A. The effect of the temperature is the result of an inherent characteristic of a silicon solar cell [15].

Figure 13. I-V Curve under Different Temperatures

Figure 14. Open Circuit Voltage as a Function of Temperatures

Figure 15. Short Circuit Current as a Function of Temperatures

Figure 16. Conversion Efficiency as a Function of Temperatures

CONCLUSIONS

In the work, the simulation of a silicon solar cell has been done by the PC1D program. The performance of the solar cell can be obtained from the equation of the conversion efficiency. By studying the effect of each of thickness and impurities concentration for the n-si emitter region, where the best performance of the solar cell was at the thickness and impurities concentration at $0.002\mu\text{m}$, 10^{20}cm^{-3} , respectively. So that it turns out that the emitter region must be very thin, in order to allow the passage of most of the photons of light falling on the cell to the base region and then the process

of generation electron- holes pair. The optimum values for thickness and impurities concentration in the base region were 300 μm , 10^{16}cm^{-3} , respectively. The increase of the solar cell temperature led to a decrease in the open circuit voltage and conversion efficiency. On the other hand, an increase in temperature can leads to a slight increase in the short-circuit current of the silicon solar cell.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Chuan, L. Tianze, Z. Xia, and H. Luan, "Simulation of silicon solar cell using PC1D," *Advanced Materials Research*, vols. 383–390, pp. 7032–7036, 2012, doi: 10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.383-390.7032.
- [2] H. Haug *et al.*, "A graphical user interface for multivariable analysis of silicon solar cells using scripted PC1D simulations," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 38, pp. 72–79, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.egypro.2013.07.257.
- [3] M. Zerrirgui Djamel, "Analyse de l'impact des différentes couches antireflets sur l'efficacité de conversion d'une cellule solaire en mono-silicium," 2020.
- [4] C. S. Solanki, *Solar Photovoltaics: Fundamentals, Technologies and Applications*, 3rd ed. New Delhi, India: PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd., 2015.
- [5] P. Lopez-Varo *et al.*, "Device physics of hybrid perovskite solar cells: Theory and experiment," *Advanced Energy Materials*, vol. 8, no. 14, Art. no. 1702772, 2018, doi: 10.1002/aenm.201702772.
- [6] O. Isabella, K. Jäger, A. H. M. Smets, A. C. M. M. van Swaaij, and M. Zeman, *Solar Energy: The Physics and Engineering of Photovoltaic Conversion, Technologies and Systems*. Cambridge, U.K.: UIT Cambridge, 2016.
- [7] O. O. Ogbomo, E. H. Amalu, N. N. Ekere, and P. O. Olagbegi, "A review of photovoltaic module technologies for increased performance in tropical climate," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 75, pp. 1225–1238, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2016.11.109.
- [8] I. M. Ahmed, O. I. Alsaif, and Q. T. Algwari, "The general properties of solar cells generations—Quantum dot as study case," *NTU Journal of Engineering and Technology*, vol. 2, no. 3, 2023.
- [9] P. Singh and N. M. Ravindra, "Temperature dependence of solar cell performance—An analysis," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, vol. 101, pp. 36–45, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.solmat.2012.02.019.
- [10] K. Jäger, O. Isabella, A. H. M. Smets, A. C. M. M. van Swaaij, and M. Zeman, "Solar energy fundamentals, technology, and systems," *Green Energy and Technology*, pp. 159–214, 2014, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-03073-8_6.
- [11] M. Belarbi, A. Benyoucef, and B. Benyoucef, "Simulation of the solar cells with PC1D application to cells based on silicon," *Advanced Energy: An International Journal*, vol. 1, pp. 1–10, 2014.
- [12] H. Naim *et al.*, "An in-depth optimization of thickness of base and emitter of ZnO/Si heterojunction based crystalline silicon solar cell: A simulation method," *Journal of Electronic Materials*, vol. 51, pp. 586–593, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s11664-021-09255-9.
- [13] N. Selmane, A. Cheknane, and H. S. Hilal, "A numerical simulation to achieve a high efficiency: Influence and optimization of thickness and doping concentration of emitter layer of heterojunction solar cells," *Journal of Sciences and Engineering Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 2, 2020.
- [14] P. Lin, L. Lin *et al.*, "Numerical simulation of $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_4$ based solar cells with In_2S_3 buffer layers by SCAPS-1D," *Journal of Applied Science and Engineering*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 383–390, 2014.
- [15] F. Dincer and M. E. Meral, "Critical factors that affecting efficiency of solar cells," *Smart Grid and Renewable Energy*, vol. 1, pp. 47–50, 2010, doi: 10.4236/sgre.2010.12008.

